

Malignant Middle Cerebral Artery Infarction Secondary to Traumatic Internal Carotid Artery Dissection: A Case Report.

Vitor Carneiro de Vasconcelos Gama*, Igor Pacheco Fiuza Romeiro, David Augusto Batista Sá Araújo, Christian Max Uchoa Leite, Carlos Eduardo de Melo Oliveira, Melina Lima Braga, Samuel Soares Coutinho, Igor Pinheiro Barros

Faculty of Medicine, Federal University of Ceara, Brazil

Citation: Vitor Carneiro de Vasconcelos Gama, Igor Pacheco Fiuza Romeiro, David Augusto Batista Sá Araújo, Christian Max Uchoa Leite, Carlos Eduardo de Melo Oliveira, Melina Lima Braga, et al. Malignant Middle Cerebral Artery Infarction Secondary to Traumatic Internal Carotid Artery Dissection: A Case Report. *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour.* 2024;3(01):1-7.

Received Date: 15 Jan, 2024; **Accepted Date:** 19 Jan, 2024; **Published Date:** 21 Jan, 2024

***Corresponding author:** Vitor Cornelio de Vasconcelos Gama, Faculty of Medicine, Federal University of Ceara, Brazil

Copyright: © Vitor Carneiro de Vasconcelos Gama, Open Access 2024. This article, published in *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour (ICMCRJ)* (Attribution 4.0 International), as described by <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

ABSTRACT

Internal carotid dissection is an important cause of ischaemic stroke in those aged under 50 years. The case of a 25-year old male patient with acute onset neurological symptoms at approximately six hours after a blunt head trauma is reported. A brain CT scan revealed right medium cerebral artery (MCA) territory ischaemic lesion. Based on Doppler ultrasonography and clinical findings, the diagnosis of a right internal carotid dissection was established. The patient presented with a progressive worsening of his neurological status. Several days after admission, the control CT scan revealed malignant right cerebral artery infarction that required decompressive craniotomy. Together with this case, the clinical manifestations, aetiologies, diagnostic and therapeutic options and outcomes of carotid artery dissection are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Traumatic dissection of the carotid arteries is an uncommon and potentially life-threatening condition. It can often go unnoticed, due to the unremarkable associated traumatic event and the delayed onset of neurological signs and symptoms.

CASE REPORT

A 25-year-old male patient had a blunt head trauma following a motorcycle and vehicle collision accident, arriving at the Hospital 1 hour later (day 1), where he was diagnosed as having a mild Traumatic Brain Injury (mTBI), being kept under clinical surveillance for 2 hours and then discharged home. The patient reported being asymptomatic at home at approximately 5am of day 1. In the morning of that day, he was found unconscious at home, being brought to the local hospital, where he presented with bradycardia, altered mental status and a left hemiparesis.

His past medical history was unremarkable.

Given this new neurological presentation, he was then sent to a more specialized center. By the time the patient arrived in the more specialized center, he was already out of the time window for thrombolysis or thrombectomy.

A thorough neurologic evaluation showed left-sided hemispatial neglect, left tactile, visual and auditory extinction, left complete and disproportionate hemiparesis with brachiofacial predominance, apraxia of eyelid opening, left-sided pyramidal signs and a partial Horner's syndrome (miosis, partial ptosis, pseudo-enophthalmos, without anhidrosis or flushing of the face). The left-sided pyramidal signs included hyperreflexia, presence of the triple flexion response (flexion of the thigh, leg, and dorsiflexion of the foot, indicating profound dysfunction of the pyramidal tract, with a spread of the reflex to the L3 and L2 myotomes) when elicited by the plantar reflex maneuver.

The patient had a score of 17 on the NIH scale and of 13 Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS).

The patient's first brain CT (performed in day 2, approximately 30 hours after the accident) was compatible with malignant infarction, demonstrating a right middle cerebral artery hyperdensity and a cortico-subcortical hypodensity in the right frontotemporoparietal area (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The first Brain CT showed the hyperdense right middle cerebral artery sign, as well as a cortico-subcortical hypodensity in the right frontotemporoparietal area suggestive of infarction.

A Doppler ultrasound examination of the carotid arteries and cervical vessels was then performed (given the neurological signs of Horner syndrome), revealing dissection of the right carotid bulb (with pseudo-lumen) extending longitudinally, as well as an intraluminal hematoma (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Doppler ultrasound examination of the carotid arteries showing right carotid bulb dissection, extending longitudinally, forming a pseudo-lumen, as well as an intraluminal hematoma.

Daily brain CT and Transcranial Doppler (TCD) Sonography were performed. Approximately 72 hours following hospital admission, the patient's neurologic status deteriorated. By that time (day 5), the patient showed progressive decrease of level of consciousness (GCS 6; increase in the NIH score from 17 to 24) as well as signs (clinical and imaging) of worsening intracranial hypertension. There was sonographic evidence of carotid bulbar dissection. The measurement of the Optic Nerve Sheath Diameter (ONSD) using Ultrasonography showed values of 6.0mm and 4.5mm for left and right NOSD, respectively, a finding suggestive of increased intracranial pressure. The TCD Sonography showed the T-pattern of the ICA occlusion (occlusion of the distal portion of the intracranial ICA) with extension of the occlusion to M1 of the right MCA (artery-arterial embolism). New brain CT scan showed well established hypodensity in the territory of the right MCA (ASPECTS score of 4) as well as significant increase in the midline shift (**Figure 3**).

Figure 3: Brain CT scan, axial sections revealing right middle cerebral territory infarction, with important mass effect and significant a 1.2cm midline shift. Hyperdense middle cerebral artery sign is visible (a, yellow arrow).

The patient underwent decompressive craniectomy, given the severity of his neurological deficits and the imminence of parenchymal herniation. The control CT scan, after decompression, showed normal midline (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Centralized midline and no evidence of parenchymal herniation can be found in the postoperative brain CT.

The patient was discharged home 2 months later with neurological sequelae, as well as multiple complications related to the long stay at the ICU. At hospital discharge, 65 days after craniectomy, the patient had a modified Rankin Scale (mRS) of 3.

DISCUSSION

The dissection of the cervical arteries is responsible for approximately 2% of all ischemic cerebrovascular events and up to 25% of stroke in young adult patients. The ICA is divided into four segments based upon anatomic landmarks: Cervical, Petrous, Cavernous and Cerebral. There is no consensus whether it is the ICA or the vertebral arteries to be more commonly dissected [1,2].

MECHANISM AND RISK FACTORS

Given that dissection usually takes time to manifest any sign or symptom, with 25-50% of patients presenting with first neurological deficits only after 12h, efforts have been made to determine scenarios with high likelihood of a cerebrovascular injury. The mechanism of head trauma, among

other risk factors, can suggest if the patient will benefit from additional imaging studies. Blunt cerebrovascular injury can result from motor vehicle crashes (more than 50%), falls, assaults, and strangulation, and even ground-level falls (two-thirds of blunt cerebrovascular injury in patients 65 years and older) [3-6].

The majority of dissections in trauma result from minor or trivial injury, only rarely resulting from major head or neck trauma. The incidence of BCVI is clinically significant in elderly ground-level fall (EGLF) patients and figures as an independent predictor of mortality [3,7].

Bilaterality occurs in 13-25% of injuries [3,5,8].

Regarding ICA, there are well known mechanisms of injury in blunt trauma, with the most common being the hyperextension or contralateral rotation of the head and neck, in which the ICA is stretched across the lateral processes of C1-C3 [4,9].

Upper cervical spine fractures were the most common risk factor for BCVI in EGLF patients. 7 Cervical spine fracture has the strongest association with blunt cerebrovascular injury [11].

A total of 260 patients with CSfx were evaluated, 168 high-risk pattern of injury for BCVI and 92 patients with low CSfx (C4-C7) without risk factors for BCVI. A diagnosis of BCVI was made in 13% and 2%, respectively. This study even proposed that all CS fracture patterns warrant screening for BCVI [10].

CLINICAL PRESENTATION

The majority of patients with BCVI do not have neurologic symptoms at presentation but may develop signs or symptoms hours or days later.

Cervical bruit in the young, expanding cervical hematoma, neurologic deficits such as hemiparesis, transient ischemic attack, Horner syndrome, oculosympathetic paresis, vertebrobasilar insufficiency are all signs that require prompt evaluation for BCVI.

In the case the patient presented with Horner syndrome (ptosis, myosis, anhidrosis). Blunt carotid injury can disrupt the periarterial sympathetic plexus, leading to this condition. Thus, although pupillary asymmetry can have a number of etiologies in the trauma patient, blunt cerebrovascular injury should be suspected ipsilateral to the side of the smaller pupil if the larger of the pupils is reactive and the smaller pupil is not [12].

SCREENING

The onset of the first neurological sign is variable, and efforts have been made to screen patients with high likelihood of a BCVI. The Denver criteria figures as the most commonly applied and was recently expanded to include more injuries as risk factors [13,14].

The Denver criteria were initially developed in 1996, modified in 2005 to limit the types of cervical spine injuries that qualify, and expanded in 2012 to include additional craniofacial, brain, and

thoracic injuries. Subsequently, the Denver criteria have been further expanded to include again all cervical spine fractures [1,2,3,15,16].

Patients diagnosed with blunt cerebrovascular injury should receive antithrombotic therapy (aspirin or heparin) to decrease the risk of stroke and stroke-related mortality.

The cost of long-term rehabilitation care and human life after BCVI-associated neurologic events is substantial. Surgeons caring for the multiply injured should screen for carotid and vertebral artery injuries in high-risk patients. Suggested that aggressive angiographic screening for BCVI based on a patient's injury pattern and symptoms allows for early diagnosis and treatment and is cost-effective because it prevents ischemic neurological events (INEs) [17].

At hospital discharge, the patient had a modified Rankin Scale (mRS) of 3. Even though trauma was the patient's starting event, the Glasgow Outcome Scale (GOSE - designed to assess disability resulting directly from TBI) was not used in this case, given that the direct cause of the brain injury and subsequent disability in this patient was the stroke [18,19].

CONCLUSION

Missing the diagnosis of carotid artery dissection can be disastrous for patients, which oftentimes are young, leading to various complications, including malignant stroke, resulting in a high disability burden. Physicians must be aware of this potentially life-threatening condition, and Hospitals must raise awareness of BCVI risk factors that demand surveilling imaging in victims of trauma.

REFERENCES

1. Robert B Goodwin, Paul R Beery 2nd, Ronald J Dorbish, J Andrew Betz, Jayesh K Hari, Judy M Opalek, et al. Computed tomographic angiography versus conventional angiography for the diagnosis of blunt cerebrovascular injury in trauma patients. J Trauma. 2009;67(5):1046.
2. Eastman AL, Chason DP, Perez CL, McAnulty AL, Minei JP. Computed tomographic angiography for the diagnosis of blunt cervical vascular injury: is it ready for primetime? J Trauma. 2006;60(5):925.
3. Biffi WL, Ray CE Jr, Moore EE, Franciose RJ, Aly S, Heyrosa MG, et al. Treatment-related outcomes from blunt cerebrovascular injuries: importance of routine follow-up arteriography. Ann Surg. 2002;235(5):699.
4. Carter DA, Mehelas TJ, Savolaine ER, Dougherty LS. Basal skull fracture with traumatic polycranial neuropathy and occluded left carotid artery: significance of fractures along the course of the carotid artery. J Trauma. 1998;44(1):230.
5. Edwards NM, Fabian TC, Claridge JA, Timmons SD, Fischer PE, Croce MA. Antithrombotic therapy and endovascular stents are effective treatments for blunt carotid injuries: results from long term followup. J Am Coll Surg. 2007;204(5):1007.

6. Cogbill TH, Moore EE, Meissner M, Fischer RP, Hoyt DB, Morris JA, et al. The spectrum of blunt injury to the carotid artery: a multicenter perspective. J Trauma. 1994;37(3):473.
7. Anto VP, Brown JB, Peitzman AB, Zuckerbraun BS, Neal MD, Watson G, et. Blunt cerebrovascular injury in elderly fall patients: are we screening enough? World J Emerg Surg. 2018;13:30.
8. Lee VH, Brown RD Jr, Mandrekar JN, Mokri B. Incidence and outcome of cervical artery dissection: a population-based study. Neurology. 2006;67(10):1809-12.
9. Zelenock GB, Kazmers A, Whitehouse WM Jr, Graham LM, Erlandson EE, Cronenwett JL, et al. Extracranial internal carotid artery dissections: noniatrogenic traumatic lesions. Arch Surg. 1982;117(4):425.
10. Kopelman TR, Leeds S, Berardoni NE, O'Neill PJ, Hedayati P, Vail SJ, et al. Incidence of blunt cerebrovascular injury in low-risk cervical spine fractures. Am J Surg. 2011;202(6):684-8; discussion 688-9.
11. Kim DY, Biffi W, Bokhari F, Brakenridge S, Chao E, Claridge JA, Fraser D. Evaluation and management of blunt cerebrovascular injury: A practice management guideline from the Eastern Association for the Surgery of Trauma. J Trauma Acute Care Surg. 2020;88(6):875.
12. Sturzenegger M. Spontaneous internal carotid artery dissection: early diagnosis and management in 44 patients. J Neurol. 1995;242(4):231-8.
13. Clay Cothren Burlew, Walter L Biffi, Ernest E Moore, Carlton C Barnett, Jeffrey L Johnson, Denis D Bensard. Blunt cerebrovascular injuries: Redefining screening criteria in the era of noninvasive diagnosis. J Trauma Acute Care Surg. 2012;72(2):330.
14. Bensch FV, Varjonen EA, PyhältöTT, Koskinen SK. Augmenting Denver criteria yields increased BCVI detection, with screening showing markedly increased risk for subsequent ischemic stroke. Emerg Radiol. 2019;26(4):365.
15. Miller PR, Fabian TC, Croce MA, Cagiannos C, Williams JS, Vang M, et al. Prospective screening for blunt cerebrovascular injuries: analysis of diagnostic modalities and outcomes. Ann Surg. 2002;236(3):386-93; discussion 393-5.
16. Berne JD, Norwood SH, McAuley CE, Vallina VL, Creath RG, McLarty J. The high morbidity of blunt cerebrovascular injury in an unscreened population: more evidence of the need for mandatory screening protocols. J Am Coll Surg. 2001;192(3):314-21.
17. Cothren CC, Moore EE, Ray CE Jr, Ciesla DJ, Johnson JL, Moore JB, et al. Screening for blunt cerebrovascular injuries is cost-effective. Am J Surg. 2005;190(6):845.
18. Wilson L, Boase K, Nelson LD, Temkin NR, Giacino JT, Markowitz AJ, et al. A Manual for the Glasgow Outcome Scale-Extended Interview. J Neurotrauma. 2021;38(17):2435-2446.
19. Newcommon NJ, Green TL, Haley E, Cooke T, Hill MD. Improving the assessment of outcomes in stroke: use of a structured interview to assign grades on the modified Rankin Scale. Stroke. 2003;34(2):377-8.